

REAL-TIME INDUSTRIAL PROCESS CONTROLLING & MONITORING USING MOBILE

P. Rohith¹, Thatikonda Shivani²,

Aluguri Sairam³, Dr. E. John Alex⁴

^{1,2,3} UG Student, Dept. of ECE, CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

⁴ Professor, Dept. of ECE,
CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

ABSTRACT

The project is aimed to design a real time industrial process monitoring and controlling system by using wireless communication technology GSM, using which the manual operations can be completely eliminated. In industries, there will be various machinery to be operated on the basis of the status of other machinery. For this purpose, a person should be employed to monitor the status of loads. But there may be chances that the person may forget to operate. And also it is not an easy task for a person to operate manually as these machines run with high currents and high power consumption. This project gives the best solution for those situations and also the manual operation will be completely eliminated. This application will be developed by using a wireless concept. Here we consider, one of the wireless communication systems, that is GSM communication system as it is very cheap and very easy to implement. A GSM modem provides the communication interface. It transports device protocols transparently over the network through a serial interface. A GSM modem is a wireless modem that works with a GSM wireless network. This GSM Modem can accept any GSM network operator SIM card and act just like a mobile phone with its own unique phone number. Advantage of using this modem will be that

you can use its RS232 port to communicate and develop embedded applications. Applications like SMS Control, data transfer, remote control and logging can be developed easily. The modem can either be connected to PC serial port directly or to any microcontroller. In this project, we will provide the automation for an industry by monitoring boiler temperature and boiler water level. This project is designed in such a way that we will interface a temperature sensor and three water level sensors to an 8 bit microcontroller. A GSM modem will be interfaced to the controller using serial communication.

INTRODUCTION

The focus of proposed system is real time monitoring of operator in workshop which is necessary for any industrial management. In recent years the focus was on machine parameter monitoring; now we are trying to design a system which is beneficial to the operators and management personnel by providing them information about machine utilization. In any industry, there are many departments. Each department may have many separate workshops. For each workshop, there may be maximum three shifts in a day. During the shift change, operators working in the workplace are relieved and entering the workplace is allocated the machines. In this case study we are trying to provide automated allocation and

monitoring of operator at work place. Normally every industry keeps two entries of the workers. First is at the entry gate of company (i.e. the time office or Personnel department) and second is at workshop supervisor register of individual worker. One is kept for salary and work hours count and later is kept for production floor monitoring or efficiency monitoring. B. Radio Frequency Identification Radio-frequency identification (RFID) is the wireless noncontact use of radio-frequency electromagnetic fields to transfer data, for the purposes of automatically identifying and tracking tags attached to objects. The tags contain electronically stored information. Unlike a bar code, the tag does not necessarily need to be within line of sight of the reader, and may be embedded in the tracked object [1]. The radio frequency identification (RFID) is the technology similar in theory to bar code identification. With RFID, the electromagnetic or electrostatic coupling in the RF portion of the electromagnetic spectrum is used to transmit signals. An RFID system consists of an antenna and a transceiver, which read the radio frequency and transfer the information to a processing device, and a transponder, or tag, which is an integrated circuit containing the RF circuitry and information to be transmitted. The key differences between RFID and bar code technology are RFID eliminates the need for line-of-sight reading that bar coding depends on. Also, RFID scanning can be done at greater distances than bar code scanning. High frequency RFID systems (850 MHz to 950 MHz and 2.4 GHz to 2.5 GHz) offer transmission ranges of more than 90 feet, although wavelengths in the 2.4 GHz range are absorbed by water (the human body) and therefore has limitations. RFID is also called dedicated short range communication (DSRC) [2]. An RFID reader's function is to interrogate RFID tags. The means of interrogation is wireless and because the distance is relatively short; line of sight

between the reader and tags is not necessary. A reader contains an RF module, which acts as both a transmitter and receiver of radio frequency signals [3].

Block diagram

ARUDINO:

The Arduino is a family of microcontroller boards to simplify electronic design, prototyping and experimenting for artists, hackers, hobbyists, but also many professionals. People use it as brains for their robots, to build new digital music instruments, or to build a system that lets your house plants tweet you when they're dry. Arduinos (we use the standard Arduino Uno) are built around an ATmega microcontroller — essentially a complete computer with CPU, RAM, Flash memory, and input/output pins, all on a single chip. Unlike, say, a Raspberry Pi, it's designed to attach all kinds of sensors, LEDs, small

motors and speakers, servos, etc. directly to these pins, which can read in or output digital or analog voltages between 0 and 5 volts. The Arduino connects to your computer via USB, where you program it in a simple language (C/C++, similar to Java) from inside the free Arduino IDE by uploading your compiled code to the board. Once programmed, the Arduino can run with the USB link back to your computer, or stand-alone without it — no keyboard or screen needed, just power.

WATER FLOW SENSOR:

Water Sensor water level sensor is an easy-to-use, cost-effective high level/drop recognition sensor, which is obtained by having a series of parallel wires exposed traces measured droplets/water volume in order to determine the water level. Easy to complete water to analog signal conversion and output analog values can be directly read Arduino development board to achieve the level alarm effect.

RELAY MODULE

Relay modules are simply circuit boards that house one or more relays. They come in a variety of shapes and sizes, but are most commonly rectangular with 2, 4, or 8 relays mounted on them, sometimes even up to a 16 relays.

Relay modules contain other components than the relay unit. These include [indicator LEDs](#), [protection diodes](#), transistors, resistors, and other parts. But what is the module relay, which makes the bulk of the device? You may ask. Here are facts to note about it:

- A relay is an electrical switch that can be used to control devices and systems that use higher voltages. In the case of module relay, the mechanism is typically an [electromagnet](#).
- The relay module input voltage is usually DC. However, the electrical load that a relay will control can be either AC or DC, but essentially within the limit levels that the relay is designed for.
- A relay module is available in an array of input voltage ratings: It can be a 3.2V or 5V relay module for low power switching, or it can be a 12 or 24V relay module for heavy-duty systems.
- The relay module information is normally printed on the surface of the device for ready reference. This includes the input voltage rating, switch voltage, and current limit.

BUZZERS

In common parlance a Buzzer is a signaling device that is not a loudspeaker. It can be mechanical, electromechanical, or electronic (a piezo transducer). BeStar produces Buzzers in every available configuration for a wide variety of applications. A Piezo transducer can produce the sound for panel mount buzzers, household goods, medical devices and even very loud sirens. When a lower frequency is required an electromagnetic buzzer can fill the need. These are very common in automotive chimes and higher end clinical diagnostic devices. The BeStar buzzer range includes self drive units with their own drive circuitry (indicators), or external drive units, which allow the designer the flexibility to create their own sound patterns.

GSM (Global System for Mobile communications)

GSM (Global System for Mobile communications) is a cellular network, which means that mobile phones connect to it by searching for cells in the immediate vicinity. GSM networks operate in four different frequency ranges. Most GSM networks

operate in the 900 MHz or 1800 MHz bands. Some countries in the Americas use the 850 MHz and 1900 MHz bands because the 900 and 1800 MHz frequency bands were already allocated. The rarer 400 and 450 MHz frequency bands are assigned in some countries, where these frequencies were previously used for first-generation systems. GSM-900 uses 890–915 MHz to send information from the mobile station to the base station (uplink) and 935–960 MHz for the other direction (downlink), providing 124 RF channels (channel numbers 1 to 124) spaced at 200 kHz. Duplex spacing of 45 MHz is used. In some countries the GSM-900 band has been extended to cover a larger frequency range. This 'extended GSM', E-GSM, uses 880–915 MHz (uplink) and 925–960 MHz (downlink), adding 50 channels (channel numbers 975 to 1023 and 0) to the original GSM-900 band. Time division multiplexing is used to allow eight full-rate or sixteen half-rate speech channels per radio frequency channel. There are eight radio timeslots (giving eight burst periods) grouped into what is called a TDMA frame. Half rate channels use alternate frames in the same timeslot. The channel data rate is 270.833 kbit/s, and the frame duration is 4.615 ms.

DHT TEMPERATURE & HUMIDITY SENSORS.

These sensors are very basic and slow, but are great for hobbyists who want to do some basic data logging. The DHT sensors are made of two parts, a capacitive humidity sensor and a thermistor. There is also a very basic chip inside that does some analog to digital conversion and spits out a digital signal with the temperature and humidity. The digital signal is fairly easy to read using any microcontroller. Humidity is the measure of water vapour present in the air. The level of humidity in air affects various physical, chemical and biological processes. In industrial applications, humidity can affect the business cost of the products, health and safety of the employees. So, in semiconductor industries and control system industries measurement of humidity is very important. Humidity measurement determines the amount of moisture present in the gas that can be a mixture of water vapour, nitrogen, argon or pure gas etc... Humidity sensors are of two types based on their measurement units. They are a relative humidity sensor and Absolute humidity sensor. DHT11 is a digital temperature and humidity sensor.

CONCLUSION

This model proposes radical change in industrial operation and operator experience. Scan-in units are provided to workshop supervisor for

smooth and faster scanning and verification of operators. RFID is embedded in the cards and this RFID is scanned by scan-in unit and scan-out unit. In RFID, an operator specific code is stored. When scanning unit encodes this code by In process or Out process, it redirects to central unit. In process updates the information of all operators available in the industry and let the central unit to make the machine reserve or vacant. Central unit allot the machines operators and if still some machines remain vacant then reflect them as available across industry from where any operator willing to work on it and can't take that machine. Apart from this In, Out and allotment process is also provided to the operators. Out process provides the operators to break his work at any situation by Out procedure and at the same time, his vacant machine are provided to a waitlisted operator. These interfaces provide capability to work at any machine within the industry. These technology inclusions in the industry bring transparency and reduce the hassles of workers while shift change.

REFERENCES

- [1] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Radio-frequency_identification.
- [2] <http://www.webopedia.com/TERM/R/RFID.html>

- [3] <http://www.rfidreader.info/>.
- [4] Siva Kumar, “Real Time Production Monitoring System”, Post Graduate Thesis, faculty of Electronics and Computer Engineering, Technical University, Malaysia.
- [5] Ognjen Marjanovic, Barry Lennox, David Sandoz, Keith Smith, Milton Crofts, “Real-time monitoring of an industrial batch process,” Science Direct, Computers and Chemical Engineering, 30 2006, pp: 1476–1481.
- [6] Rub´en Morales-Men´endez, Nando de Freitas and David Poole, "Realtime monitoring of complex industrial processes with particle filters", Visiting Scholar (2000-2003) at The University of British Columbia.
- [7] Pouria Zand, Supriyo Chatterjea, Kallol Das and Paul Havinga, “Wireless Industrial Monitoring and Control Networks: The Journey So Far and the Road Ahead”, Journal of Sensor Actuator Network, 2012, 1, 123-152.
- [8] Boong Yeol Ryoo, Hyun Chul Chung, “Wireless or Mobile Sensors for Monitoring Worker’s Health and Safety in Construction,” Department of Construction Science, Texas A and M University, Texas, USA.
- [9] Alberto Gonzalez Prieto, Rolf Stadler, “Adaptive Real-time Monitoring for Large-scale Networked Systems”, School of Electrical Engineering KTH, Royal Institute of Technology Stockholm, Sweden.
- [10] Maarten Lambertus Neelis, Monitoring Industrial Energy And Carbon Flows”, Thesis Utrecht University, Copernicus Institute for Sustainable Development and Innovation, Section Science, Technology and Society
- [11] Reddy, Kallem Niranjana, and Pappu Venkata Yasoda Jayasree. "Low Power Strain and Dimension Aware SRAM Cell Design Using a New Tunnel FET and Domino Independent Logic." International Journal of Intelligent Engineering & Systems 11, no. 4 (2018).
- [12] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Design of a Dual Doping Less Double Gate Tfet and Its Material Optimization Analysis on a 6t Sram Cells."
- [13] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Low power process, voltage, and temperature (PVT) variations aware improved tunnel FET on 6T SRAM cells." Sustainable Computing: Informatics and Systems 21 (2019): 143-153.
- [14] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Survey on improvement of PVT aware variations in tunnel FET on SRAM cells."

In 2017 International Conference on Current Trends in Computer, Electrical, Electronics and Communication (CTCEEC), pp. 703-705. IEEE, 2017

[15] Karne, R. K. ., & Sreeja, T. K. . (2023). PMLC- Predictions of Mobility and Transmission in a Lane-Based Cluster VANET Validated on Machine Learning. International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication, 11(5s), 477–483. <https://doi.org/10.17762/ijritcc.v11i5s.7109>

[16] Radha Krishna Karne and Dr. T. K. Sreeja (2022), A Novel Approach for Dynamic Stable Clustering in VANET Using Deep Learning (LSTM) Model. IJEER 10(4), 1092-1098. DOI: 10.37391/IJEER.100454.